

Using the Opportunities of Telepedagogy in Forming a Culture of International Communication in Students

Atamuratov Dilshod

Doctoral student at Urganch State University

Abstract: This article discusses the use of educational, educational, and motivational possibilities of telepedagogy in the formation of the culture of interethnic communication among future teachers. Pedagogical conditions for the development of knowledge, skills, and abilities related to this field, as well as the directions of telepedagogy, are given. Pedagogical opportunities related to the presentation of formal, informal, and referential information and which pedagogical methods are used by future teachers for the successful assimilation of television information by students were analyzed.

Keywords: future teacher, culture of international communication, telepedagogy, mass media, TV news, TV show, literature, art.

Theory. Future teachers should also master the methods of educating students in relation to reality in order to ensure effective perception of the presented materials. In this case, the materials perceived by students should meet the following requirements. Such as the existence of a stock of information, taking into account the interests of students, and corresponding to the level of culture formed by students. Therefore, it is necessary to know the methods of creating favorable pedagogical situations and effective management of these situations in order for students to effectively perceive the presented information.

The training of future teachers to use the opportunities of telepedagogy in forming the culture of international communication among students requires the organization of specific pedagogical processes. It is necessary to pay attention to the following: one of the important conditions for ensuring the effectiveness of using the possibilities of telepedagogy is to ensure systematicity; special attention should be paid to the training of future teachers to appropriately use the opportunities of telepedagogy in extracurricular pedagogical processes; in addition, the formation of the culture of analysis and perception of the information presented, especially among students of teenage age, is also of special importance; It is important for future teachers to have the competence to cooperate with parents in forming a culture of inter-religious and inter-national dialogue by watching TV programs together with students and analyzing them.

Future teachers should know the importance of the chosen topic in the successful acquisition of television information by students. It is assumed that the topics are chosen according to the purpose. The family plays an important role in learning tele-information. TV information acquired in the family circle occupies a special place in the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students. Because the family is the first link that forms formal, informal and referent groups.

Methodology. Full understanding of information is important in the formation of the culture of international communication. It is important for teenage students to choose their communication partners. Such a choice has a special place in determining their life goals. At the same time, they form behavioral models, surrounding people, motives for reaction to events. In order for future teachers to

be ready to form a culture of interethnic communication in students, they are required to improve their professional competence in the following directions:

- a) Systematically learn and apply the methods of working with parents in the family on the development of pedagogical knowledge on the formation of the culture of interethnic communication in their children;
- b) General secondary schools should know and be able to use the methods of forming the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students in the pedagogical processes of the lesson and extracurricular;
- c) Students are required to create the scripts of television shows and choose the content of educational conversations by forming the culture of inter-ethnic communication in the students through mass media.

This approach is methodologically important. Interethnic relations require the analysis of relations between peoples of different nationalities from different points of view. The culture of inter-ethnic relations is a holistic form of a set of values and norms. It is expressed in the student's perception and behavior and expands the opportunities for interaction with representatives of different nationalities. The culture of inter-national communication also represents the mutual relations between certain representatives of the same nation. For example, the relationship between representatives of culture, art, and athletes is an example of this.

The culture of interethnic communication and interethnic relations creates a basis for friendly creative relations and cooperation among representatives of literature and art based on mutual understanding. For many centuries, among the mature poets and writers of the Uzbek people, Gafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, Zulfiya, and representatives of literature and art, Jacob Kolas, Rasul Gamzatov, Parda Tursun, Mukhtar Avezov, and Karim Gurbanfasov are among today's youth. Friendly creative relations were observed as an example. Informing pupils and students of such evidence serves as a guiding factor for the continuation of these traditions. When thinking about inter-ethnic relations between individuals, the following qualities are observed: It is observed that there is a harmony of universal values and norms, that they ensure the compatibility of the behavior of the representatives of both nations, that there is a positive attitude and assessment towards the representatives of different nations, and that there is a similarity in their way of life and spiritual world.

Conclusion. On the basis of the above, it should be noted that the culture of inter-ethnic communication is a product of positive experience accumulated by members of society. This experience is created as a result of interaction between representatives of different nationalities. Because in society, representatives of different nationalities enter into mutual communication and relationships in the process of life activity. These relations arise as a result of material, political, spiritual, and certain forms of interaction. Didactic resources, educational materials, methods, and methods used in the educational process occupy a special place in the formation of these relations.

Because the culture of inter-ethnic communication is created primarily at the personal level. This is done in the process of socialization of the individual with the help of educational tools. Therefore, the culture of inter-ethnic communication embodies the qualities of tolerance of a person. The culture of international communication is formed by students in their educational activities with the help of various didactic tools and life experiences and forms the basis of the spiritual life of society.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Millatlararo munosabatlar sohasida O‘zbekiston Respublikasi davlat siyosati Konsepsiyasi (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 15-noyabrdagi PF-5876-son Farmoniga 1-ilova).
2. 2018-yil 28 - noyabrdagi PQ-4038-son “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida milliy madaniyatni yanada rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori.

3. Поштарева Т. В. Формирование этнокультурной компетентности учащихся в полиэтнической образовательной среде: автореферат дис. канд. пед. наук. – Владикавказ, 2009. – 45 с.5
4. Safarova R.G. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida madaniy muhit yordamida o'quvchilarni ma'naviy-axloqiy jihatdan rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari. T.N.Qori Niyoziy nomidagi O'zbekiston pedagogika fanlari ilmiy tadqiqot institutida o'tkazilgan "Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida madaniy muhitni yaratishning pedagogik texnologiyalari: muammo va yechimlar" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallar to'plami 117-120 betlar.
5. R.Safarova, G.Khasanova. Organizing an environment for cooperation of students in the educational process (for ensuring the development of the new Uzbekistan society). XVI International Scientific-Practical Conference "Actual Problems of Improving Farming Productivity and Agroecology" (IPFA 2024),E3S Weof Conferences Volume 538, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202453805044>
6. Омарова М.К. Культура межнационального общения как важная компетенция выпускников педагогических специальностей // Международный журнал экспериментального образования. – 2013. – № 11-1. – С. 27-29.